

The Phenylthiocarbamides. A Contribution to the Study of the Triad -N-C-S-. Part II. Action of Hydrolytic Agents on Phenylthiocarbamide.

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Phenylthiocarbamide may be expected to exist in one or more of the following forms: (*cf.* Werner, A new structural formula for thiocarbamide, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **101**, 2185; Krall, Constitution of guanidine, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 1398).

(I)

(II)

(III)

Hydrolysis provides an obvious line of attack on the problem of constitution, and might be expected to yield ammonia or aniline in varying proportions, with the simultaneous production of a compound having a hydroxyl group in place of the amino or anilino group. Experiments have shown, however, that this expectation is not realised, but that the hydrolytic reagent whether alkaline or acid produces decomposition of a dissociation type according to the following equations:—

In presence of a strong alkali changes (i) and (ii) occur simultaneously, but that represented by equation (i) largely predominates. With weaker alkalis changes (i) and (ii) still occur but that represented by equation (ii) increases at the expense of reaction (i). With water and weak acid, reaction (i) ceases altogether and (ii) predominates while the reaction represented by equation (iii) begins to be evident.

With strong acid changes (ii) and (iii) increase greatly (cf. the action of acetic anhydride on thiocarbanilide).

It is clear, therefore, that a progressive change in the pH value of the hydrolytic reagent causes a progressive change in the nature of the reaction and this may be due to a progressive tautomeric change in the constitution of phenylthiocarbamide. This will be discussed later.

In all cases varying but only small amounts of ammonia are produced and this is due to secondary changes such as the following :

which we have verified under the conditions of our experiments. There is no doubt that ammonia appears as a primary product only in the presence of considerable concentrations of acid when the characteristic pungent smell of mustard oil also shows itself.

In certain cases small amounts of thiocarbanilide are also produced, and this too is undoubtedly due to secondary changes.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of concentrated alkali.—Phenylthiocarbamide (7.6 g.) and caustic potash (25 g.) dissolved in water (50 c.c.) were taken in a distilling flask connected to a receiver through a condenser. The receiver was connected to a Volhard trap. Steam was passed for 3-3½ hours and the distillate which was alkaline to litmus collected. The residual solution when cold was acidified with dilute acetic acid, copious evolution of hydrogen sulphide took place and a white precipitate of phenyleyanamide settled down.

The potassium sulphide from a similar experiment was determined by titration with alkaline zinc solution. [Found: H_2S , 1.39 g., i.e., 81.7 % of theory as calculated from equation (i) above].

The alkalinity of the distillate calculated as ammonia gave $\text{NH}_3 = 0.114$ g. or 13.4 % of that calculated from equation (iii).

Evidently this change may be represented by the equation,

the ammonia being due to secondary changes as already stated.

Action of N-alkali and examination of volatile products.—Phenylthiocarbamide (7.6 g.) and caustic potash (2.8 g.) dissolved in water (50 c.c.) were treated as in previous experiment. The distillate was now acidic. It was redistilled with caustic potash and the evolved ammonia collected in standard sulphuric acid. The residual solution in the distilling flask deposited crystals of unchanged phenylthiocarbamide and was further found to contain thiocyanic acid, alkali sulphide and very small amount of phenylcyanamide. From a similar experiment the amounts of thiocyanic acid and the alkali sulphide were determined. [Found: H_2S , 0.40 g. (23.53%); HCNS , 0.089 g. (3.31%); NH_3 , 0.16 g. (18.82%).]

The estimation of thiocyanic acid in presence of hydrogen sulphide presented some difficulty. The procedure adopted was to acidify with dilute sulphuric acid, pass sulphur dioxide which within a minute or two decomposed the hydrogen sulphide in the cold; nitric acid then oxidised the excess of sulphur dioxide and the solution could be titrated with *N*/10-silver nitrate solution by Volhard's method.

Prolonged action of N-alkali.—Phenylthiocarbamide (30.4 g.) and caustic potash (11.2 g.) dissolved in water (200 c.c.) were refluxed and 5 g. samples were taken at intervals by means of a bucket formed from a length of silver wire and a small glass tube. The sample was cooled in a stoppered bottle, weighed and dissolved in water (25 c.c.), filtered from phenylthiocarbamide, etc., and the filtrate made up to 200 c.c. This procedure was rendered necessary by the fact that thiocyanic acid cannot be estimated in the presence of phenylthiocarbamide unless the quantity of the latter is small (separate communication). The amounts of hydrogen sulphide and thiocyanic acid were at once determined and their amounts in the total bulk of solution (*i.e.*, 241.6 g.) calculated. Thiocarbanilide was identified in small quantity and the smell of aniline was observed but no trace of mustard oil. The following results were obtained.

TABLE I.

Time.	Hydrogen sulphide.	Thiocyanic acid.
2 hours	19.61 %	10.14 %
4	28.04	11.64
8	20.81	22.51
13	11.71	35.99
18	8.69	44.05
22	1.31	52.0

FIG. 1.

These results in Table I and those plotted in Fig. 1 clearly indicate that the following two changes occur simultaneously :

The decline in the quantity of hydrogen sulphide after it has risen to a maximum remains unexplained.

Effect of varying amounts of caustic potash and of water alone.—Phenylthiocarbamide (5 g.) was refluxed with 1, $\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{8}$, $\frac{1}{16}$, 0 equivalent of caustic potash respectively dissolved in 132 c.c. of water, for 1 hour. The amounts of hydrogen sulphide and thiocyanic acid were estimated as before with the following results.

TABLE II.

Caustic potash.	Hydrogen sulphide.	Thiocyanic acid.
1 equiv.	23.20 %	5.7 %
1/2	8.67	6.8
1/4	2.29	7.0
1/8	0.86	7.9
1/16	Traces	8.7
0	Absent	8.81

This experiment shows that diminishing alkalinity favours the second change.

Action of barium hydroxide solution.—Phenylthiocarbamide (5 g.) was refluxed with 1 equivalent of barium hydroxide dissolved in 33 c.c. of water for an hour. The results obtained with one equivalent of caustic potash under identical conditions are given for comparison.

TABLE III.

Alkali.	Hydrogen sulphide.	Thiocyanic acid.
Barium hydroxide.	13.24 %	9.89 %
Caustic potash.	29.6	6.06

This experiment shows that a weaker alkali has the same effect as a more dilute alkali, *i. e.*, that the effects observed are due to the p_H values.

Action of acids.—Phenylthiocarbamide (5 g.) was heated under reflux with one equivalent of acid diluted with 50 c.c. of water for an hour. No trace of hydrogen sulphide was evolved. The percentage of thiocyanic acid was estimated. The results obtained are summed up in the following table.

TABLE IV.

Acid.	Hydrogen sulphide.	Thiocyanic acid.	Mustard oil.
Acetic	Nil	16.08 %	Faint smell.
Hydrochloric	Nil	61.85	Strong smell

SUMMARY.

1. Phenylthiocarbamide does not suffer hydrolysis of the normal type.
2. Hydrolytic agents produce decompositions of a dissociation type represented by the following equations:

3. Change No. (i) takes place only under alkaline conditions; (ii) occurs over a wide range but is favoured by increasing acidity; (iii) becomes appreciable only in the presence of strong acid.

4. In other words the carbon-sulphur bond is the first to be ruptured in the presence of alkali, the carbon-anilino in the presence of acids, the carbon-amine in the presence of the strongest acids.

Discussion of the bearing of these results on the problem of constitution is postponed pending the completion of further investigations now in progress.

Some of the above experiments were performed by Mr. G. V. Halwe, M.Sc.